

Paper 3

A Critical Review of Gratitude Intervention Effectiveness on Psychological Wellbeing

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: *Theory and research have shown that gratitude interventions have positive effect on health and on measures of psychological well-being. Gratitude listing, behavioral expressions, and creating awareness of the effects of developing an attitude of gratitude are methods of inducing gratitude. This article critically reviews different studies that have interventions with different structures suited to study different samples.*

Design/Methodology/Approach: *An extensive review of existing literature regarding, a critical review of gratitude intervention effectiveness on psychological wellbeing are used while reviewing the literature. The research articles reviewed were collected from Google Scholar.*

Finding/Result: *The uniqueness of each intervention and its effect has been critically analyzed and suggestions to introduce and test interventions as part of school value development programs have been suggested.*

Originality/Value: *The researchers tried to bring a change in the life of middle adolescents' social and emotional maturity through gratitude education.*

Paper Type: *Critical Review of Research Studies*

Key Words: Gratitude Intervention, Middle Adolescents, Critical Review, Psychological Wellbeing.

1. INTRODUCTION:

The word gratitude is derived from the Latin word 'gratia', meaning favour, and 'gratus', meaning pleasing [1]. Gratitude liberates a person from placing total responsibility in oneself. It makes a person to value everything that is generously lavished upon, without even asking for it. It is bestowed upon us without even slightest efforts on our part. The air, light, sunlight, water, nature which are so essential, for every living thing. But rarely do we realize how richly we are blessed by the universe. When we come in touch with the reality of this abundance of goodness, we feel the vibration of happiness and contentment. When we are at peace with ourselves our social life can enrich others and emotionally connect with another, accepting others as they are. We would realize how blessed we are and this realization makes us feel grateful to the supreme power (God) that governs our life. This feeling of gratitude makes us feel happy, contented and peaceful [3].

Adolescence is a time when people experience a lot of changes in biological system, emotional, physiological, social spiritual and psychological life [4]. They start to verify what they have learnt from their parents, teachers, peers, relatives and friends. Adolescence is also a time of confusion in these matters [5]. An adolescent is likely to look within for answers and solutions while coping socially and emotionally [6]. Showing gratitude is one way of coping and is one of the several factors that influence the development of social and emotional maturity [7]. Stable

social relations and emotional stability help make people live a satisfying life and ensure psychological wellbeing [8].

Are feelings of gratitude innate or learned [9]? One can only examine the effect of a nurturing environment, such as providing gratitude education and assess if there is any significant increase in the feelings of gratitude [10].

In this study the researchers' aim is to study the impact of gratitude education on the social and emotional maturity of middle adolescents. The researcher intends to develop an intervention package which could be used as a supportive measure in the classroom to enhance social and emotional maturity among middle adolescents. The intervention package should help middle adolescents to cope with social and emotional challenges with ease and experience adulthood with confidence and a sense of satisfaction.

2. REVIEW OF ARTICLES:

The present review focuses on studies that examine social and emotional maturity and several other relevant variables associated with levels of gratitude among middle adolescents.

A study titled "What good is gratitude in youth and schools? A systematic review and meta-analysis of correlates and intervention outcomes" was conducted by Tyler, Renshaw, Rachel, Steeves [11]. The study systematically reviewed and meta-analyzed original empirical journal articles investigating gratitude in youth through September 2014 (N = 20). Findings from the meta-analysis of correlates indicated small-to-moderate convergent and discriminant evidence for gratitude as a subjective well-being indicator in youth, other results indicated that gratitude measures have relatively poor test-retest reliability and/or predictive validity and that they have questionable concurrent validity with other gratitude measures. Moreover, findings from the meta-analysis of intervention outcomes indicated that gratitude-based interventions are, as a whole, generally ineffective and that much more intervention research is warranted. Implications of these findings for theory, future research, and the practice of school psychology are discussed.

John, Rindfleisch&Froh [12] studied the impact of gratitude on adolescent materialism and generosity. They presented two studies conducted among over 900 adolescents that revealed a promising strategy for decreasing materialism: fostering gratitude. In Study 1, results from a nationally representative survey showed that children and adolescents with a grateful disposition were less materialistic. In Study 2, experimental evidence showed that an intervention designed to increase gratitude (i.e. keeping a gratitude journal) significantly reduced materialism among adolescents and also attenuated materialism's negative effect on generosity. Using real money and donation as a behavioral measure, they found that adolescents who kept a gratitude journal donated 60% more of their earnings to charity compared to those in the control condition. The implications of the findings, offer some suggestions for putting the results into action, and provide an agenda for future research in this domain.

Froh, Yurkewicz and Kashdan [13] in their study on gratitude and subjective well-being in early adolescence: Examining gender differences examined gratitude among 154 students to identify benefits from its experience and expression. Students completed measures of subjective well-being, social support, prosocial behavior, and physical symptoms. Positive associations were found between gratitude and positive affect, global and domain specific life satisfaction, optimism, social support, and prosocial behavior; most relations remained even after controlling for positive affect. Gratitude demonstrated a negative relation with physical symptoms, but not with negative affect. Relational fulfillment mediated the relation between gratitude and physical symptoms. Gratitude demonstrated strong relations with the following positive effects: proud, hopeful, inspired, forgiving, and excited. The relation between gratitude and family support was moderated by gender, indicating that boys, compared with girls, appear to derive more social benefits from gratitude. Strengths, limitations, and implications are discussed.

In a study on being grateful is beyond good manners: Gratitude and motivation to contribute to society among early adolescents Jeffrey, Froh, Giacomo Bono and Emmons, longitudinally examined early adolescents' gratitude and their social integration, or motivation to use their strengths to help others and feel connected to others at a macro level. Middle school students (N = 700) completed measures of gratitude, prosocial behavior, life satisfaction, and social integration at baseline (T1), 3-months (T2), and 6-months (T3) later. Using bootstrapping to examine multiple mediators, controlling for demographics and social integration at T1, the researchers found that gratitude at T1 predicted social integration at T3 and that prosocial behavior and life satisfaction at T2 mediated the relation. Further meditational analyses showed that gratitude and social integration serially enhanced each other and that

gratitude may help to initiate upward spirals toward greater emotional and social well-being.

A study on the effects of counting blessings on subjective well-being: a gratitude intervention in a Spanish sample by Martínez-Martí, Avia and Lloreda [14] examined a gratitude intervention repeating Emmons and McCullough [15] study in a Spanish sample. Participants were randomly assigned to one of three conditions (gratitude, hassles and any event) and kept daily records during 2 weeks of gratitude, affect, quality of relationships, physical and subjective well-being. We added design features to assess the intervention long-term impact (follow-up measures), and to improve the design control (pre-treatment measures). Following the cited authors' analysis, i.e., comparing groups only in the post-test, we replicated their results, finding differences in positive affect and gratitude between the gratitude condition and the hassles condition. However, when including both the pre and the follow-up measures in the analysis, results were replicated only partially, as the difference in gratitude disappeared. Moreover, the difference in positive affect between groups in the post-test seemed to be influenced mainly by a decrease in positive affect in the hassles group. Post-test differences between groups in positive affect disappeared in the follow-up. Gratitude interventions may have an effect on well-being, but we consider other methods to promote gratitude besides gratitude journals should be tested.

Khanna and Singh [16] examined the Effect of Gratitude Educational Intervention on Well-Being Indicators Among North Indian Adolescents. The aim of the study was to determine the impact of a gratitude building intervention on adolescents' gratitude and well-being indicators. The sample comprised 177 students aged 11–14 years (M Age = 12.29 years, SD = 0.67, 58 % male) attending two schools in North India. Using quasi-experimental design, participating classrooms from both schools were randomly allocated to intervention group (n = 95) or control group (n = 82). Participants completed an assessment battery comprising measures of well-being, positive and negative affect, life satisfaction, gratitude and cognition of benefit-appraisal at pre-test and post-test. Intervention group attended 30-min-long weekly sessions based on the gratitude curriculum for five consecutive weeks while control group attended neutral sessions for the same duration. Analysis of covariance was used to examine the differences between the intervention and control groups at post-test. Results suggested significant intervention effects on psychological well-being, positive affect, positive feelings, life satisfaction and gratitude. The cascading effect of gratitude was also observed.

Another study on Nurturing grateful and connected twenty-first century learners: development and evaluation of a socially oriented gratitude intervention conducted by Imelda, Caleon, Ronnel, King, et al, [17] aimed to develop and examine the effects of a socially oriented gratitude intervention (SOGI) on secondary students' gratitude level and interpersonal relationships. To these ends, they used a quasi-experimental research design: The experimental group (n=46) participated in the two-week intervention during a class subject focusing on character and citizenship education (CCE) while the wait-list control group (n=57) went on with regular CCE activities. All participants completed a questionnaire a week before and a month after the implementation of the SOGI and control activities. The changes in relatedness scores were statistically significant in relation to parents and peers, but not in relation to teachers. In particular, the experimental group generally maintained the quality of their relationship with their parents and peers while the control group reported a decline in these relationship domains. The change in gratitude levels did not differ significantly between the experimental group and control group, but the effect size associated with the mean gratitude change of the experimental group was found to be larger than that of the control group and comparable to what is commonly reported in other published gratitude intervention studies. The students' feedback reveals the social, cognitive and affective benefits of the SOGI.

A study on Enhancing cognitive and social–emotional development through a simple-to-administer mindfulness-based school program for elementary school children: A randomized controlled trial by Schonert-Reichl, Kimberly, Oberle, Eva Lawlor, Abbott, Thomson, Oberlander, Tim, Diamond and Adele [18] hypothesized that a social and emotional learning (SEL) program involving mindfulness and caring for others, designed for elementary school students, would enhance cognitive control, reduce stress, promote well-being and prosociality, and produce positive school outcomes. To test this hypothesis, 4 classes of combined 4th and 5th graders (N = 99) were randomly assigned to receive the SEL with mindfulness program versus a regular social responsibility program. Measures assessed executive functions (EFs), stress physiology via salivary cortisol, well-being (self-reports), prosociality and peer acceptance (peer reports), and math grades. Relative to children in the social responsibility program, children who received the SEL program with mindfulness (a) improved more in their cognitive control and stress physiology; (b) reported greater empathy, perspective-taking, emotional control, optimism, school self-concept, and mindfulness, (c) showed greater decreases in self-reported symptoms of depression and peer-rated aggression, (d) were rated by peers as more prosocial, and (e) increased in peer acceptance (or sociometric popularity). The results

of this investigation suggest the promise of this SEL intervention and address a lacuna in the scientific literature—identifying strategies not only to ameliorate children’s problems but also to cultivate their well-being and thriving.

Singh, Pant and Dhyani [19] studied the Role of Economic Class in Ascertaining Social and Emotional Maturity of Adolescents by assessing and comparing the social and emotional maturity of 277 randomly drawn class XI students of Pantnagar, Uttarakhand across family economic class. A self-designed questionnaire was used to study the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents of the present study. Social and Emotional maturity of the respondents were assessed employing Rao’s Social Maturity Scale and Emotional Maturity Scale [20], respectively. The study revealed that adolescents from higher and upper middle class family were significantly more personally adequate than those from rest of the classes whereas, on social adequacy component, adolescents from higher class were observed to be significantly lower than those from rest of the family classes. Adolescents from higher income family were seen to be significantly more socially adjusting and independent than those specifically from lower income family. On the whole adolescents from higher income family were seen to be significantly more emotionally mature in comparison to the ones from other classes. Social maturity and emotional maturity were found to be significantly and positively correlated with each other across family economic class.

3. REVIEW AND CRITICAL ANALYSIS:

Most of the studies reviewed by the author have used gratitude interventions and have tested its efficacy in influencing different psychological factors. The interventions have been developed by the researchers and have been tailor made to cater to the specific sample. The duration of the intervention varied across all studies. In the study by Bausert, Froh, etal [21] the authors aimed at developing a theoretical model and examined the importance of gratitude in the personal and social life during the developmental phase. The study reports reviews of various studies which stress the usefulness of gratitude. The review conducted by the authors is fairly extensive and therefore the findings reflects the real need to include gratitude interventions during the developmental phase as the factors influencing healthy gratitude development needs to be understood better. The review of the relation between gratitude and subjective well-being from both a hedonic and eudemonic perspective suggests other researchers to focus their research on these less researched aspects of subjective wellbeing.

The study by Czyżowska and Gurba [22] examined the effect of gratitude in understanding the meaning in life, psychological well-being, health and stress. Prepared diaries were to be maintained as part of the intervention by male and female adults. The reports of participants in the diaries were to focus on specific observations through the day. This would have helped the participants in the experimental group to personalize gratitude better and could be the influencing factor in significantly improving psychological well-being, environmental mastery, relationships with others and purpose in life. Significant decrease was also noted in anxiety/insomnia and depression symptoms as well as in perceived stress.

Klibert, Rochani, Haresh and Samawi[23] studied the effect of gratitude on college students. The uniqueness of this study is the introduction of a positive experience exercise as the intervention .The researchers then assessed its effect on the experimental group. The finding supported the hypothesis that gratitude maintains positive emotions resulting from a positive experience.

Michael and Jermaine [24] examined the impact of a gratitude intervention on mental well-being during COVID-19. The COVID 19 pandemic was a common stressor across the world. A well timed study of the effect of gratitude, on a universal stressor. Whether the participants were personally affected by Covidm19, whether they were infected themselves or had lost a significant other has not been mentioned in the study. This relevant variable could have altered the findings.

The study on ‘Gratitude and Well-Being: Who Benefits the Most from a Gratitude Intervention?’ which was conducted by Rash, Matsuba, Prkachin [25], followed a pre post experimental design wherein the experimental group had to daily maintain a positive and negative report during the intervention period which the researchers referred to as gratitude contemplation intervention program . The control group was made to recall and record only memorable events. The participants in the gratitude condition reported higher satisfaction with life and self-esteem. Therefore actively recording positive and negative experiences and feeling could enhance long-term well-being then just recalling memorable events.

The 6-week longitudinal study on 385 Indian adolescents by Iqbal and Dar [26] is one of the few studies on

gratitude effectiveness on self-esteem. The immediate and long-term payoffs of practicing specific Positive Psychology Interventions were examined after the participants were guided through a 2 week intervention which was to be practiced at home. This carrying over of an intervention practice to one's home could act as a relevant independent variable. The extent to which a participant takes the intervention seriously and follows instructions of the researcher would depend on factors beyond the researcher control. The findings stated the effect of counting ones blessing had a positive impact on adolescents who were low on self-esteem. The intervention helped promote subjective well-being over time.

Gratitude intervention to enhance well-being in older adults was studied by Killen and Macaskill [27]. The researchers provided online and paper delivery of interventions. Older adults preferred online interventions. Therefore more researchers could provide online interventions as this study shows there is no significant difference between online and paper delivery of the intervention.

A study which explored the implementation of a 90-min Attitude of Gratitude workshop among 51 athletes (Gabana, Steinfeldt, Wong, Chung and Svetina 2019)[28] assessed levels of state gratitude, psychological distress, life satisfaction, sport satisfaction, athlete burnout, and perceived available support in sport thrice, the week before, immediately after, and 4 weeks post intervention. This extended assessment after 4 weeks post intervention assesses whether the effect of the intervention is long lasting. Although the findings show significantly positive effect of intervention the researcher has suggested researchers to explore and study gratitude interventions in applied sport psychology.

Bono, Mangan, Fauteux and Sender [29] stated that adolescents face unprecedented wellbeing challenges, and many schools are underprepared to meet these needs and therefore social emotional learning (SEL) programs help. Therefore they adopted a modern approach while developing the intervention for high school students. They stressed that gratitude interventions should be delivered by teachers as part of the classroom routine, emphasize on expressing thanks, use social media for the intervention and create a broad experience of gratitude that is personally and socially valued within school contexts. The intervention delivery seems to be not only structured but having a teacher than a psychologist to provide the intervention gives a chance for students to participate without any hesitation in a familiar setting.

The review of the studies made in this article clearly indicates that many other psychological factors could be managed better with gratitude interventions. Incorporating gratitude interventions as part of value development sessions in primary school could be considered to get a young mind to feel grateful for several things life has to offer. Creating awareness of the benefits of feeling and expressing gratitude at an early age can develop a habit and common practice of having an attitude of gratitude for all challenges and experiences one faces in the crucial developmental stages of life.

4. CONCLUSION:

The review of the studies made in this article clearly indicates that many other psychological factors could be managed better with gratitude interventions. Incorporating gratitude interventions as part of value development sessions in primary school could be considered to get a young mind to feel grateful for several things life has to offer. Creating awareness of the benefits of feeling and expressing gratitude at an early age and in a school setup as part of co-curricular value development sessions can help inculcate the common practice of having an attitude of gratitude for all challenges and experiences one faces in the crucial developmental stages of life.

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